
Rajadharma and Viksit Bharat: Revisiting Ahilyabai Holkar's Governance through Indian Knowledge Systems

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Abstract Punyashloka Rajmata Devi Ahilyabai Holkar (1725-1795), the queen of Malwa, is widely regarded as a just ruler and a brilliant administrator. Her approach to administration respected and incorporated cultural and spiritual traditions balancing moral obligation basing her choice on the Indian Knowledge system. She used pragmatic methods to ensure justice, stability as wellbeing of the people of her reign. Her governance was exclusively people-centric and ahead of its time. She advocated for decentralization, accessible justice and other economic possibilities of growth during her reign. There is arguably no doubt that her ideas are still applicable today. This research analyzes her leadership style from the standpoint of the Indian knowledge system and links it to India's Viksit Bharat vision which embodies a prosperous, inclusive and self-reliant Economy by 2047. It examines her work in women empowerment and welfare, infrastructure, trade, agriculture & education all of which indicate her dedication to Rajdharma (The duty of the Monarch) and Yogakshema (The welfare of People). Her focus on leadership, gender parity, and culturally grounded education provides substantial insights for modern Sustainable development. It is also noteworthy how traditional knowledge might prove useful in offering direction for contemporary government in context to her endeavours.

This paper emphasizes Devi Ahilyabai Holkar's legacy as a visionary whose ideas continue to provide a Road map to modern day governance. Her leadership demonstrates how India's history holds a powerful significance to influence the country's path to "Viksit Bharat".

Keywords: Ahilyabai Holkar, Indian Knowledge System, People-Centric Governance, Viksit Bharat, Sustainable Development

Introduction

India's past has been adorned with threads of leadership that goes beyond time, offering timeless design for governance, equity, and preservation of culture and heritage which is quite essential for realizing the ambitious Viksit Bharat by 2047 vision. As the Prime Minister Narendra Modi envisioned India as a developed and self-reliant country (Atmanirbhar Bharat) focuses on inclusive growth, and technological advancements, this program targets being economically at par with global leaders while safeguarding the cultural heritage (Prime Minister Modi). And at the very core of this project lies the revival of Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS), promoting synthesis of ancient Indian knowledge of Vedas and Shastras with modern day innovation to guarantee sustainable progress.

Devi Ahilyabai Holkar, who ruled for 28-years over Malwa (1767-1795) amid the times of the Third Battle of Panipat (1761) demonstrates that synthesis. Ruling from the modest town of Maheshwar, she transformed a region of chaos into a reign of prosperity and faith, her policies which displayed classic example of rajadharma where in

it was the sovereign's moral responsibility and duty to uphold justice and ensure the well being of its subjects as outlined in Kautilya's Arthashastra (c. 4th century BCE). Ahilyabai's administration was a dynamic experiment which decentralized power, there was outstanding foresight for infrastructural development, and social upliftment, all held up by her devotion to Shiva and an immense respect for dharma (Chaurasia 245-47).

This paper revisits Devi Ahilyabai's governance finding its roots in IKS while also finding correlation and relevance of it in Viksit Bharat, Devi Ahilyabai Holkar's rule can be said have been rooted in Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS) it offers lessons for modern education policies like NEP 2020. Despite personal and political challenges, her ideas of yogakshema, which is people's safety and well-being, were ensured through open courts and projects like stepwells, as noted in John Malcolm's Memoir of Central India (1823) (Malcolm 112-15). Her approach is a classic example of how leadership comes from ethics, not force.

In the rapid age of urbanization and digital advancements, her emphasis on accessible justice and development of all members of the community provide antidotes to inequality. Viksit Bharat prioritises sustainable development which includes eco friendly infrastructure development, digital literacy, and gender equality. Devi Ahilyabai's legacy illuminated a path where tradition made way for progress, ensuring India's development has her roots in its tradition and Indian knowledge system.

2. Life and Ascension to Power

Ahilyabai Holkar's journey from being brought up in a rural background to becoming the queen of Malwa is a tale of determination and of alliances that were mutually beneficial, in an era when Maratha was in its turbulent phase. She was born on May 31, 1725 in a small village of Maharashtra, Chondi, to Mankoji Rao Shinde, a Patil, or the village headman. While the children of her age were busy in childlike activities she was immersed in unconventional education that involved literacy, arithmetic, ethical education along with more such knowledge that was necessary for an all round development of a child here. She was a curious child who equally had logical reasoning. This was recognised by her father. This foundation was rare in 18th-century India, with female literacy being low in rural areas, which made a place in minds about how education is a revered tool to acquire justice. (Sahapedia).

At the young age of eight, while Malhar Rao Holkar, a brilliant maratha Senapati under Peshwa Bajji Rao I, was on his routine pilgrimage to Jejuri Temple, Devi Ahilyabai caught his eye while she was inquiring about rituals and traditions with a composure not very common to a child as young as her. He was so impressed by her that he betrothed her to his son Khanderao, formalizing the marriage in 1733. This marriage catapulted her into being intrigued into Maratha empire, where she accompanied her husband and father in law, on campaigns, after being trained in diplomacy, logistics, and warfare and the skills that blurred gender norms when the dynamics of power were concerned in the political realm(कर्तव्य) By her early twenties, Ahilyabai was not just the daughter in law of Holkars but also a confidante, managing household as well as the state finances.

Catastrophe struck the Holkars in 1754 when Devi Ahilyabai's husband, Khanderao was attacked by cannon fire at the Battle of Kumbher, leaving their son Male Rao orphaned and sinking Devi Ahilyabai into widowhood at the age of 29. Despite the societal pressures for sati which was a traditional practice prevalent in those times, which her father in law Malhar Rao did not allow. But she embraced ascetic life and retreated to the banks of the river Narmada for meditation simultaneously also aiding Malhar Rao's expeditions (Malcolm 118). Under his guardianship, she sharpened her administrative skills, overseeing supply chains and dispute resolutions. These were among the few experiences that foretold how efficient her queenship will be in future. Malhar Rao's death in 1766, then followed by her son Male Rao's death in 1767, ignited a crisis of succession. Opportunistic nobles who were eyeing Malwa's Deccan plateaus, contested her claim.

Yet, Ahilyabai's judgement prevailed. With the support of her loyalists and after securing Peshwa Madhavrao I's support, she ascended the throne on December 11, 1767, in Maheshwar, she then nominated her brother-in-law Tukoji Rao Holkar as senapati to command the strong army of the Kingdom (Chaurasia 250). Her accession to the throne amid all the post war chaos also demanded attention from the threats that were coming from various kingdoms. Ahilyabai's spirituality which was manifested in her daily Shiva puja and various pilgrimage served as a balance, which indicated the embodiment of a ruler who was a steward of cosmic harmony and fit the archetype of The Dharmaraja as the Manusmriti commands the sovereign's righteousness (Nagrale 285). Her

policies like tax remissions for the underprivileged, women empowerment by ensuring the women receive rights on deceased husband's property and/or allowance. Her efforts to bring those who were underprivileged to mainstream etched her name in history for eternity.

3. Administrative Reforms and Governance Model

Ahilyabai Holkar's administration resembled modern federalism with a central governance being balanced and having the local governance being free to an extent, reflecting the spirit of Indian Knowledge System being put into governance models. The saranjam system was a system where land was allotted from the revenue, and troops were to be maintained based on that and sent whenever they were needed for a campaign(Nd). Devi Ahilyabai too rented land to the chiefs of the army that could be for training of military service, with regular checks so that rebellions could be prevented, this can be said to have been inspired by the mandala theory of alliances of Kautilya. When this system was applied across many Malwa villages, it gave local panchayats judicial and financial powers, which in turn reduced corruption and sped up justice.

Along with other sectors under her rule, agriculture too thrived. She built many stepwell reservoirs, including a ghat on the Narmada, in order to facilitate irrigation and prevent droughts. The taxes crops were kept low, following Arthashastra's fair principles. Her vision and welfare oriented rule turned Maheshwar into a textile center, supporting numerous weavers and artisans who produced Maheshwari sarees that were exported to ports like Surat and other parts of the country.

Her army constituted Maratha cavalry and Bhil infantry, and the soldiers defended Malwa without seeking conquest. Justice was central to her rule. In Maheshwar's open-air court, she heard cases from dawn, delivering justice to everyone from underprivileged to the elites alike. She worked to protect women's property rights (stridhan) and banned sati in her kingdom. Ahilyabai promoted inclusivity and unity among her people by including Bhil tribals in border patrols and granting them land, which reduced caste barriers. She used her personal spending fund for most public and social works. Through diplomacy with Peshwas and Mughal, she ensured peace under her rule. Unlike Europe's theory of divine-right rulers, her leadership focused on service for the welfare of her people and that made Malwa prosperous, peaceful and just kingdom.

4. Alignment with Indian Knowledge Systems

Devi Ahilyabai Holkar's rule was in a broad sense a reflection of Indian Knowledge System (IKS), where ethics blended with rajadharma and bhakti ensured a peaceful three decade long peaceful reign during her rule, where Malwa enjoyed prosperity, stability and welfare oriented governance. Her policies were well aligned with Kautilya's Arthashastra, which emphasizes yogakshema, where the well being of people is ensured. She built numerous ghats, dharmashalas and pilgrim paths that connected sacred sites, which facilitated the paths for devotees to travel. These projects along with being practical were also a strong statement that supported the sanatana dharma after temple destructions that the Mughals did, her contribution to restoration of Kashi Vishwanath Temple in Varanasi (1780) strengthened cultural identity. Since temples, as per Arthashastra, served as community centers that fostered cultural unity, imparted knowledge of the scriptures and promoted social values.

Manusmriti's dharmaraja is a sovereign who embodies the spirit of Shakti and Karuna (compassion), both of which were abundantly prevailing in Devi Ahilyabai as a ruler.

Though not directly from Arthashastra but she did apply the knowledge it provides relating to administration, to ensure her kingdom was the most peaceful one for over twenty eight years amidst the times of chaos all over India at that time. Devi Ahilyabai didn't follow rigid rules. She infused the Indian Knowledge Systems with knowledge other than indigenous prevailing during her era for example Maratha guerrilla tactics with French military drills to get more efficient results. Her deep devotion towards Shiva brought a spiritual outlook to her rule, making sure her decisions were for the greater good of the people of her kingdom. She demonstrated through her administration which was a very good example of how The Indian Knowledge System serves as a guide not just for education but also for administration and how it can prove to be a setting stone for a more development and self-reliant Bharat in this age.

5. Social and Cultural Contributions

Devi Ahilyabai's social standing was revolutionary, where the rule was of the efficient not determined by birth or hierarchical structure which led to a diverse and inclusive Malwa. In series of her social reforms foremost is her women's reforms where she renounced and prohibited sati via 1772 firman framed as a violation of dharma and promoting widow remarriage with dowry grants, she liberated thousands from pyres ensuring widow were safeguarded. When we talk about Culturally, her legacy is prolific reconstructing numerous temples, from Badrinath's shrine to Rameshwaram's corridors, not only did she mend places ravaged by Mughal but also have written orders that ensures everyone living in peace and harmony (Chaurasia 255-57). Arts and crafts flourished under her rule, Maheshwari weaving tradition was supported by her where royal dues were used, the artisans used intricate designs that combined patterns of geometry as well as icons that were devotional, sustaining thousands of artisans. Her philanthropy was also one of her major quality, she donated tons of grain yearly to pilgrims, and sheltered strays in goshalas.

She was a tolerant ruler, the tribals as well as the common people all were content in her reign. This inclusivity can be traced back to being rooted in vasudhaiva kutumbakam philosophy of Bharat, she reduced caste tensions by including the tribals. What is Devi Ahilyabai's legacy? It is a society where trade flourished, there was justice, Dharma prevailed, devotion and inclusivity were whose strong pillars, and one where marginalized were brought to the mainstream.

6. Relevance to Education and Viksit Bharat

Devi Ahilyabai's model of governance somewhat connects in a broader aspect with Viksit Bharat 2047, as per Prime Minister Modi's strong direction for making India a \$30 trillion economy (Prime Minister Modi). Her decentralisation of governance that had local panchayats maintaining the gram level administration which enabled justice that was accessible to even the marginalised. Digital India's e-panchayat portals, providing services for numerous ruralites all across the countries (NITI Aayog 12). When talked about educationally, her gurukul style school, where shastras were combined with agriculture, align with NEP 2020's IKS curriculum, which mandates credits in yoga, Ayurveda, and Arthashastra, making way for the people of India to become skilled global citizens with strong roots. (Ministry of Education 14-16; Tilak 112). Integrating Devi Ahilyabai's biography could motivate this further through case studies on ethical governance and politics, Gender Studies which gives a definite focus on Women in Administration, foreshadowing the initiative Beti Bachao Beti Padhao's STEM quotas, where female enrollment increased significantly since 2015. In the matters of infrastructure, her kund networks also aligns with Jal Jeevan Mission which counters the problem of water shortage for 96.2 million households (jal jeevan mission). Further where Maheshwar's Economic stability is concerned, it can be said to match the initiative of Atmanirbhar Bharat's MSME hubs, aimed at providing employment for 110 million people by 2047. As the course of everything that exists in this world there are hurdles that persist. There needs to be a mention of Devi Ahilyabai in text books for we have an immense lot to learn from her timeless administration that is still prevalent in this age and time. For Amrit Kaal, (the period of the next 25 years as stated by Prime Minister Modi in 2021) the curriculum combining her dharma with AI ethics could produce leaders balancing profit and yogakshema, ensuring Viksit Bharat's vision blossoms.

7. Conclusion

Devi Ahilyabai Holkar's governance which was deeply rooted in the ancient Indian Knowledge system transformed Malwa into an excellent model of justice, prosperity and welfare, offering insightful future reference for Viksit Bharat. Her legacy urges educational reforms to mergetraditional wisdom with modern technology, new age learning , ensuring the development of the country and its people is holistic and value driven. Future research should explore archives of the then records of governance etc, for deeper insights, and authentic narratives. The ancient Indian knowledge system has time and again proven its relevance when applied to modern times, not just in the field of education but also in the field of Medicine, Science and even in global governance models. By studying and learning more about the IKS and how such prominent rulers applied it to their administration, India will be able to build a future that balances modernity with its proud and rich heritage.

References

- [1]. Malcolm, John. *A Memoir of Central India, Including Malwa, and Adjoining Provinces*. Vol. 1, Kingsbury, Parbury, and Allen, 1823.
- [2]. Nagrale, N. N. "Ahilyabai and Her Benevolent Administration." *Annals of the Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute*, vols. 58–59, 1977–78, pp. 283–92. JSTOR, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/44142025>.
- [3]. Chaurasia, Radhey Shyam. *History of the Marathas*. Atlantic Publishers, 2004.
- [4]. Hritambhara, and Hritambhara. "Ahalyabai Holkar | Hritambhara." Hritambhara, 13 Aug. 2020, hritambhara.com/2019/05/31/ahalyabai-holkar-the-saint-queen-of-malwa.
- [5]. Ministry of Education, Government of India. *National Education Policy 2020*. Government of India, 2020, https://www.education.gov.in/sites/upload_files/mhrd/files/NEP_Final_English_0.pdf.
- [6]. Tilak, Jandhyala B. G. "Integrating Traditional Indian Knowledge System in Education: NEP 2020 Perspective." *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, vol. 7, no. 7, 2024, pp. 110–20.
- [7]. Nd. "Saranjam – NDHistories." NDHistories, 11 Feb. 2024, ndhistories.wordpress.com/tag/saranjam.
- [8]. "Sahapedia: Maharani Ahilyadevi Holkar." Sahapedia, <https://map.sahapedia.org/article/Maharani-Ahilyadevi-Holkar/2576>. Accessed 18 Sept. 2025.

